

USE OF NEW INNOVATIVE MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6654080>

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Annotation: *This in the article school t a`lim in the system mathematics fannini in teaching new innovative modern information technology use about statement reported .*

The key words: *mathematics , innovation , innovation education , technology , profit , modernization .*

A of society the future his inseparable part and vital zarurati which was education of the system which degree development with determined . Uzbekistan Republic presidents Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev as he said "If you ask me you what It hurts ? " if you ask , our children education and The answer is upbringing beraman degan from his words to this more a karra is an example . Today kunda independent development out of the way hurry growing of our country continuous education system correction to do and improvement , new quality to the stage raise him _ advanced pedagogical and new innovative modern information technology current to do and they are through education efficiency increase today of the day current issues is one .

School education today The task of teachers new innovative information technologies through lesson treatment effective using to students information clear and understandable so delivery give is _

Therefore also a lesson for during teacher of students mathematics fanini understandable clear so studied lessons in progress new innovative modern information technology using formed reach and teaching to the goal is appropriate .

School education mathematics in the system science in teaching new technician tools , this including computer _ and other information technology jadal enter coming current period fanlararo membership provision in order to informatics fani achievements use formed reach of students knowledge get efficiency increase very much big help gives.

Computer techniques school education institutions application to teach _ process optimization wide the way open gives.

Next on per year school education in the system mathematics fanini in teaching from computers and new innovative modern information technology use a how much

basic directions take went . To them computer using knowledge evaluations , various type teacher programs functional exit and develop , learn oid mathematical games functional exit and others kind of again new of students mathematics fanini independent own on performance for help giving modern innovative applications functional was released . These programs and video lessons through students lesson during taught topics more strengthen to receive very much big help gives.

Current kunda school education in the process new innovative modern information technology use and uni training in the process apply which was curiosity was attention day by day intensify is going on , like this to be reasons one , this until traditional in education school students only ready knowledge take over taught if new _ innovative modern information technologies them occupying knowledge themselves looking for independent study and analysis even if they do the conclusions themselves quoting issue teaches . Teacher this in progress person development , formation , knowledge take and to be brought up conditions creates and this with a in a row management , directing function does.

New innovative modern information technologies students knowledgeable , mature and sciences deep assimilation provides .

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